

TEENAGE PREGNANCY PREVENTIVE PROGRAMS IN TABACO CITY, PHILIPPINES: LISTENING TO THE SIDE OF MAJOR PLAYERS IN HEALTH POLICIES AND IMPLEMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Teenage pregnancy has been a global concern; the Philippines, for one, is also struggling to find solutions to its rising teenage pregnancy rates. Teenage pregnancy is a factor in complications in pregnancy and childbirth leading to maternal mortality. Teenage pregnancy causes stigma and stress to the family and results in additional financial burden to the teenager's own family due to unplanned or mistimed birth. This is a phenomenological qualitative research method. It is focused on experiences of the participants involved in teenage pregnancy prevention. The participants include six nurses and two key informants who were selected through purposive sampling. One-on-one interview were done. Audio recording was used in the interviews. Coding was utilized in treating the participants. The information collected was categorized and thematized. Results showed that there is no specific program on teenage pregnancy prevention in Tabaco City but there are interventions done include trainings of youth leaders, conduct of adolescent congress and forum, and modified family development sessions. Strategies found effective are involving communities, collaborating with other institutions, and engaging the youth. While experiences that need improvement are skills in monitoring and evaluation, research, and communication. Challenges met that affect their performance of implementers are work overload, lack of manpower, limited resources, challenge in sustaining the program during change in leadership, training the wrong personnel, and lack of confidence among teachers and parents to discuss sexuality. Along implementation of policies, the challenges include poor relationship of the legislator with the executive, lack of skilled implementers, and the need for more young people in the field. In conclusion, there is a need to strengthen the strategies found to be effective and to address the challenges experienced. There is a need for a strong legislative and executive support to teenage pregnancy prevention which can be maximized through a comprehensive teenage pregnancy prevention program.

Keywords: *Teenage, pregnancy, prevention, preventive programs, health policies*

Introduction

Adolescence is a crucial phase of human development and teen pregnancy has a tremendous impact on the education, social, and economic lives of young parents and their families. Being around adolescents as a teacher and working in adolescent and youth health projects for the past three years, the proponent of this study has seen that the health of teenagers and teenage pregnancy stimulated interest in the field of health. This interest happens not only because of biological and social aspects that define the adolescent health, but also because this interest

ignites, above all, the start of adolescent health promotion, health education, access to information and services, and skills building like communication skills and youth leadership of the adolescents.

Teenage pregnancy is one of the most serious concerns among the young people. Biologically, every pregnancy by teenager is high risk that may lead to complications and even death of the young mother and her child. When women give birth in their teen years, they are at a higher risk of the baby being born early or prematurely. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) (2014) pregnancy and childbirth complications are the second cause of death among 15 to 19 year olds globally. Some 3 million unsafe abortions among girls aged 15 to 19 take place each year, contributing to maternal deaths and to lasting health problems.

Furthermore, socioeconomically, becoming parents at a young age generally affects the adolescents lives and dreams. Many girls who become pregnant drop out of school. A girl with little or no education has fewer skills and opportunities to find a job. This can also have an economic cost to a country losing out on the annual income a young woman would have earned over her lifetime if she had not had an early pregnancy (WHO, 2014).

Teenage pregnancy is a global concern. The World Health Organization states that teenage pregnancy in low- and middle-income countries are the highest (WHO, 2017). In the Asia-Pacific region, the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) says that the Philippines is the only country where the rate of teen pregnancy is rising over the last two decades. Study says teen pregnancies, high youth unemployment and the slow decline of the overall fertility rate in the Philippines may deprive the country of the faster economic growth that usually comes from having more working-age people than younger and older dependents (Philippine Star, 2016).

Early childbearing increases the risks for both mothers and their newborns. In low- and middle-income countries, like the Philippines, babies born to mothers under 20 years of age face a 50% higher risk of being still born or dying in the first few weeks versus those born to mothers aged 20-29. The younger the mother, the greater the risk is to the baby. Newborns born to adolescent mothers are also more likely to have low birth weight, with the risk of longterm effects (WHO, 2014).

In the Philippines, one in ten young Filipino women age 15-19 has begun childbearing: 8 percent are already mothers and another 2 percent are pregnant with their first child according to the results of the 2013 National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS, 2013). In actual numbers, there were a total of 383,194 live-births by teenagers 15-19. In Region V (Bicol Region), The Young Adults Fertility Survey of 2013 (YAFS4) reported that of the 1,102,940 youth population in Region V, more than 280,000 youth have engaged in sex. Of the 301,235 females, age 15-19 years old, 26,500 began child-bearing (YAFS4, 2013).

Tabaco City is one of the first cities in the country to legislate an Adolescent Health ordinance. Still, despite the existing programs for young people, teenage pregnancy is still a problem. In 2013, Tabaco city recorded 171 teen pregnancies; 315 in 2014; 228 in 2015; and 260 in 2016.

As an educator, the researcher believes the fact that the young of today are the future resource of the nation. Ensuring that our teenagers have access to health services and education is a way to make sure that they maximize their potentials. Health education and specific nursing interventions to address teenage pregnancy may help young people delay coital debut and therefore address teenage pregnancy.

Despite initiatives, still the evidence shows that pregnancy is still rising. Looking at the efforts of Tabaco City and identifying the gaps though this study will benefit the City Government, program implementers, community health workers and nurses, and, will help in addressing the rise in teenage pregnancy.

Synthesis of the Art

Nurses should be involved in implementing programs that have an impact on delaying of sexual intercourse and focus on education on teaching teens skills to prevent pregnancy, and in managing teenagers, the intervention should facilitate promotion of self-worth and enable them to see themselves as valuable, contributing members of their communities -- help-givers rather than help-seekers (Applewhite 2003; Gurgel, Alves, Ximenes, Vieira, Beserra, & Gubert, 2011; Horizon Solution Site, 2013). Linking teenage pregnancy programs to research and practice, evaluation studies of pregnancy prevention programs indicate that many are ineffective or not well evaluated, and this is a huge gap in sexual health data among adolescents since sexual and reproductive behaviors are generally self-reported, and are, therefore, subject to underreporting (Johns, Moncloa, & Gong 2000; Darroch, Woog, Bankoleand & Ashford, 2016).

Majority do not proactively discuss sexuality issues with service users. Over 90% of nurses understood how patients' diseases and treatments might affect their sexuality, but 80% did not take time to discuss sexual concerns, and 60% did not feel confident in their ability to address patients' sexual concerns (Dyer & das Nair 2012; Saunamäki, Andersson, & Engström 2010). Social norms in society were an obstacle to opportunities for health professionals to feel comfortable and act professionally, hence, the majority of nurses had a high awareness of the importance of sexual healthcare, but rarely felt knowledgeable or comfortable discussing sexual health issues with adolescents (Klaeson, Hovlin, Guvå & Kjellsdotter, 2017; Yip, Sheng, Chan, Wong, Wai-Yee Lee, & Abraham, 2015). A study suggests that when nurses use their knowledge and go beyond their comfort zone and address sexuality, they can identify patients' sexual problems, especially that patients' sexuality is still surrounded by silence - but factors exist that can facilitate discussion of sexuality and the nurses have a key role in detecting ill-health (Saunamäki & Engström, 2013). Also, student nurses who underwent a public health nursing course in which adolescent sexual health education is incorporated showed significant improvements and prepared them as parent-based adolescent sexual health educators - a core competency for community health nurses working with families in communities and across all health care delivery settings (Santa Maria, Markham, Crandall & Ramos, 2016).

In addition, the health workers described their experience with teenagers as challenging due to the formers' limited skills when it comes to addressing adolescent-specific needs, and professionals and health-care services need to adopt strategies and demonstrate characteristics which create environments that are more supportive of sexuality (ZariRukundo, Abaasa, Natukunda, Ashabahebwa & Allain, 2015; Bauer, Haesler & Fetherstonhaugh, 2015). Communication is an important skill for a nurse especially in dealing with adolescents' sexuality problems to aid in addressing teenage pregnancy. Regarding clinical practice, a variety of personal and contextual reasons limit the nurses' willingness to talk about sexuality with patients, such as gender and age differences, familial upbringing, lack of time and privacy, and restricted perception of nursing role. All nurses stressed the need for further specialized training not only in physiology issues related to sexuality, but also, most importantly, in communication skills (Nakopoulou, Papaharitou & Hatzichristou, 2009). The training program for sexual healthcare could exert positive and beneficial effects on nurses' development of knowledge regarding sexual healthcare and clarify their values and attitudes. Also it is fundamental to sexual history taking

and the management of sexual problems as it improves their level of comfort in dealing with sexual issues, like teenage pregnancy and sexual activities of young people; exposure to sexual health courses; and psychosocial orientation. Moreover, health professionals personal sexual attitudes are also important factors affecting their involvement in sexual health (Sung, Jiang, Chen & Chao 2016; Tsimtsiou, Hatzimouratidis, Nakopoulou, Kyrana, Salpigidis & Hatzichristou, 2006). It is worth noting that professionally prepared health educators were found to be significantly more likely than their counterparts to teach about teenage pregnancy risks, teenage pregnancy impacts, finding information/services related to pregnancy, including finding information/services related to HIV, and HIV diagnosis/treatment. These topics were significantly more likely to be taught in health-only classes versus combination classes (Rhodes, Jozkowski, Hammig, Ogletree, 2013).

Research indicates that when adolescent females have sex at a young age with much older partners, there is a greater chance that their first sexual experience was involuntary or unwanted and that they can become pregnant. Almost 80% of first instances of early sex of young people were unprotected, while girls were more likely to not use any form of protection during their first sexual encounters (Aruda, Waddicor, Frese, Cole, & Burke 2010; Punongbayan 2014). The risks for babies or children born to teenage mothers are fetal deaths, child abuse and neglect, abortion, negative health, negative cognitive and behavioral outcomes, and lack of proper nutrition, healthcare, and cognitive and social stimulation (World Vision, 2017). Adolescent girls who already had their pregnancy had more clearly developed longer-term plans for the future with focus on career while girls who had never gotten pregnant shared aspects of their future orientation, and focused on developing the competencies of girls to access social, economic and cultural capitals may be an effective way of tackling the threat of teenage pregnancy than focusing only on their vulnerability and associated risks (Bell, Glover & Alexander 2013; Ahorlu, Pfeiffer & Obrist, 2015). While focusing on males to address teenage pregnancy and improve young men's overall wellness, healthcare providers should routinely address sexual health and health (Vargas, Borus & Charlton, 2017).

Teenage pregnancy risk is strongly linked to sexual abuse, especially for males and those who have experienced both incest and non-familial abuse. Furthermore, the cross-cutting risk factors include female gender, younger age, substance use/abuse, family constellation, parent-child conflict, and mother disengagement (Saewyc, Magee & Pettingell 2004; Francisco, Hicks, Powell, Styles, Tabor & Hulton 2008). Likewise, socioeconomic factors like low education, low income of a teen's family, few opportunities for positive youth involvement may contribute to high teen birth rates (CDC, 2016). Unfortunately, in the Philippines, adolescent reproductive health services have not been given the attention they badly need, and there is an absence of concrete programs from government, both national and local, in responding to this growing concern among adolescents (Lagman-Luistro & Lagman, 2013). The statistics, according to registered psychologist Ms. Rosario Verdán, is a result of several factors: lack of communication between parents and their children, repeated exposure to visual portrayal of sex on TV, film, and the internet, and peer influence within the *barkada* (peers) (Abanes, 2017).

The single most important effect of teenage childbearing is a lower educational attainment of the teenage mother, both in the short and long run. As a result, households of those females who had their first child as teenagers tend to have a lower income per capita (Gomez & Vazquez, 2014).

Education needs to happen at home, and parents may help by reinforcing and supplementing what teens learn in school. Parents can set the stage for a lifetime of healthy sexuality and both adolescents and their parents preferred that parents should be the ones to teach their children

about sexual matters and inform them about the risks that may ensure. However, parents were not comfortable nor confident to discuss issues of sexuality and inherent risks with their own children (Mayo Clinic 2014; Magowe, Dithole & St. Lawrence, 2014). The involvement of family and other caring adults matters when it comes to affecting a teenager's sexual behavior and the risk of early pregnancy. Family involvement maximizes the effectiveness of pregnancy prevention programs (Moncloa, Gong, Russell, Lee & West, 2003). Parent involvement is considered necessary in the prevention of teen pregnancy prevention and preventing other adolescent risk behaviors. Both parents and youth sought ways to improve connections and communication with each other; however, these served as obstacles to parent participation (Silk & Romero 2013; Flores, Montgomery & Lee, 2005). Moving forward, educational facilities and parents should work hand-in-hand in building activities and programs that would provide sufficient knowledge for children and teenagers not to engage in activities inappropriate for their ages like sexual intercourse (Salvador, Sauce & Rosario 2016).

There is a school of thought that sex education increases sexual activity; but studies show that this is not the case. In fact, effective and successful sex education programs can decrease sexual activity and can increase contraceptive use in sexually active youth and these correct and age-appropriate information will eliminate the curiosity among adolescents and will make them aware of the consequences of sexual activity and help them veer away from such (Dangal 2006; Simon & Quilala, 2013). However, school-based program like a culturally tailored curriculum still faced a series of challenges, including implementing the intervention as part of the regular school curriculum in schools with diverse populations; low attendance when delivered as an after-school program; and resistance on the part of schools to specific curriculum content (Kelsey & Layzer, 2014). In addition, a film-based intervention for young men which aimed for participants to: know and engage the target population and engage gatekeepers in addressing contextual complexities; know the targeted behaviors and model a process of change; and look beyond development to evaluation and implementation - showed significant results in providing young people with educational information and opportunities for communication with peers and parents, skills practice, reflection, and anticipatory thinking (Aventin, Lohan, O'Halloran & Henderson, 2015). Research-based sexual health and relationships education programs when conducted by trained and empathic educators have shown to delay the time of first sexual intercourse resulting in young people reporting on better communication in their relationships (St. Leger, Young, Blanchard & Perry, 2010).

Common barriers to program sustainability include: lack of materials and supplies, insufficient funding (at the school and district level), lack of support and/or parental opposition, and other school/district priorities. School leaders also identified several needs to continue teenage pregnancy prevention programming, including continued funding, trainings, outcome/effectiveness data to support the program, and regularly updated curriculum (Craft, Brandt & Prince, 2016). Also, there are certain factors at health system and community levels that influenced the health centers' efforts to implement evidence-based clinical practices for adolescent health care support. Health center leadership, communication between leadership and staff, and staff attitudes and beliefs were reported as factors that facilitated the implementation of new practices (Hallum-Montes, Middleton, Schlanger & Romero, 2015).

Research and evidence-based practice has shown that teenage pregnancy cannot be addressed through a single intervention or service as much of teenage pregnancies are unplanned. Instead community-wide campaigns to prevent adolescent pregnancy and childbearing are needed because practitioners work with complex social issues such as teenage pregnancy, violence,

alcohol, and substance abuse and other health related issues (Teasdale 2014; Moncloa, Johns, Gong, Russell, Lee & West, 2003).

In addressing teenage pregnancy, it is important for individuals to be involved in public awareness, planning, implementation and evaluation of programs that would build sustainable development (Salvador, Sauce, Alvarez & Rosario, 2016). Community partnerships are vital in addressing teenage pregnancy issues. Collaborative leadership must identify appropriate partners, engender their cooperation, and support their staff to further the overall goals of the collaboration, including efforts of the religious sectors which could be strengthened in molding values among youth by incorporating elements of adolescent reproductive health education, the life-planning, and the peer counseling strategy (Flores, Montgomery & Lee, 2005; Commission on Population - Regional, 2014). Avoiding such pregnancies will require a fundamental shift in life chances such that delaying pregnancy offers significant socioeconomic advantages (Hewagegana, Salway, Piercy & Samarage, 2014).

In addition, community health nurses as educators may collaborate with the academe to develop strategies in educating the young people along sexual health to prevent early sex and teenage pregnancy and a good example succeeded through a unified effort to enable prospective health educators to become competent in teaching methodology, theory, practice of pedagogy, content, and skills, specific to sexuality education - in which the higher education will play a key role in ensuring the success of these standards (Barr, Goldfarb, Russell, Seabert, Wallen & Wilson, 2014).

Adolescents consider teenage pregnancy prevention as something positive; however, adolescents do not proactively seek assistance to obtain information about the topic. Therefore, it is essential to raise awareness and promote professional training in order to implement actions that are in line with public policies in a creative and innovative way so as to establish a link (Fiedler, Araújo & de Souza, 2015). Investing in adolescent health and welfare programs is vital to ensure that services are available through sustainable funding support and legislated policies (Mendes, Plaza & Wallerstein, 2014). While knowledge and self-reported behaviors frequently change with interventions, including those performed at the community level, educational programs and direct contraceptive provision, downstream outcomes rarely reflect a significant effect of the interventions (Philipps & Mbizvo, 2015). While the Intervention Now to Eliminate Repeat Unintended Pregnancy in Teenagers (INTERUPT) found no evidence to indicate that existing interventions to reduce repeat teenage pregnancy were effective, subsequent births were reduced by home-based interventions (Whitaker et.al. 2016).

All young people need comprehensive sexuality education to prepare them for healthy adult relationships, and sexuality education programs should increase adolescents' knowledge. It is worth noting that a study showed that teenage pregnancy rates were 39% lower among young individuals receiving an intervention than in those receiving standard practice or no intervention (Advocates for Youth 2008; Harden, 2009).

To improve adolescent health interventions, potential effective interventions and areas of research for adolescent health and well-being include interventions for adolescent sexual and reproductive health, nutrition for pregnant adolescents and interventions for substance abuse, sexuality-related issues like STIs, HIV, and teenage pregnancy (Salam, Das, Lassi & Bhutta, 2016; Goesling, Colman, Trenholm, Terzian & Moore, 2014). Furthermore, evaluation efforts related to performance improvement and measuring long-term impact are an essential part of attempting to

implement an effective teen pregnancy prevention intervention and determine if the initiative is an adolescent health intervention worth replicating (Tevendale, Condrón, Garraza, House, Romero, Brooks & Walrath, 2017). The Seminar on Adolescent Pregnancy and the First 1000 Days held in Metro Manila in September 2013 suggested that studies are needed to find ways to improve adolescent health and to effectively prevent and deal with unwanted pregnancies among adolescents, including developing adolescent-friendly health centers and information and education materials to increase reproductive and health awareness among youth and health workers (Capanzana & Aguila, 2015; Javier, 2015; Mendoza & Santos-Abalos, 2015).

Engaging and involving the adolescents as peer educators can be an important educational mechanism for teaching students information and skills to promote sexual health as a teenage pregnancy prevention strategy (Layzer, Rosapep & Barr 2017). The You-for-You (U4U) Teen Trail Initiative is a communication campaign to prevent early sex among teens, which aims to broaden the knowledge of Filipino youth on delaying sexual debut, preventing teen pregnancy and avoiding sexually transmitted infections. Likewise, the Local Government Unit (LGU) and the Barangay LGU can work hand-in-hand to provide training for the youth, which can start at the barangay level (Commission on Population 2017; Retalado, 2008).

In an article from the Department of Education Camarines Norte Division, a school nurse suggested to provide sexual health education to establish adolescent-friendly spaces to help prevent teenage pregnancy by disseminating the right information about the risks and impacts of early pregnancy on the teenage mother and the infant (Yanto, 2016). The Teen Health Kiosks in Cavite could help young people to understand better the preventive measures that can help avoid risky behaviors, as it is equally helpful to the community, more importantly to the adolescents, in raising awareness about avoiding bad decisions (Mendoza, 2015). In the experience of Iloilo Province and the local government units (LGU) of Marikina and Quezon City, a vital lesson learned when establishing a teen center or an adolescent health program to address sexuality-related problems and health issues is the need to obtain a Department of Education national or regional order or an LGUs legislation or Executive Order (EO) to ensure full buy-in of the community and the school authorities (Jimenez, Divinagracia, Marco, Sescon, Buenaventura, Deacosta, Enrera & Yubia, 2016).

Problem in the Field

The review of related literature and studies presented a number of problems in the field. Gaps, issues, and problems faced by program implementers, adolescents, families and the community, including the government, private agencies and schools were identified:

1. Sexual health (baseline) data gaps
2. Gaps in linking program implementation to research, monitoring and evaluation
3. Gaps in communication and advocacy skills of nurses and program implementers
4. Lack of technical skills along responding to adolescent sexual health needs
5. Need to strengthen policy mechanism supportive of sexual and reproductive Health programs
6. Need to focus of programs which will provide skills to young persons and accessible services to them
7. Lack of reliable and accessible sexual and reproductive health information
8. Cultural barriers to openly talk about the issue within the family, inside the health facility, and other settings

9. A number of existing promising success which can be replicated and scaled-up
10. Substantive misconceptions about sex education which need to be corrected

Research Gap

The findings of the studies previously conducted showed related issues which this study pursued that is, to address teenage pregnancy. However, this study specifically considered the existing programs and interventions, health policies and challenges in the implementation of the programs and policies. No same study has been conducted in Tabaco City. This study used existing information and documents which the Tabaco City Local Government Unit provided. Specifically, existing city ordinance was obtained and health interventions being conducted by the city health unit and other agencies were taken into account.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to bridge the gap in addressing teenage pregnancy in Tabaco City through community health nursing. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions: 1) What is the status of teenage preventive programs, 2) What are the experiences of the implementers of teenage preventive programs; 3) What are the challenges met in implementing a) health policies, and b) health programs? and 4) What measures can be proposed to have a comprehensive health program and policies for teenage pregnancy prevention?

Theory

This study is anchored on two theoretical models: the Precede-Proceed Model by Lawrence Green and the Health Promotion Model by Andrew Tannahill. Green's Precede-Proceed Model is based on the premise that health education, policies and environmental factors determine health and healthy behavior. On the other hand, Tannahill's Health Promotion Model suggests health promotion as three overlapping spheres of activity: health education, health protection and prevention.

Guided by the theoretical models, this study moved towards reviewing and addressing policies and programs to help address teenage pregnancy in Tabaco City, specifically, in finding possible solutions in bridging the gaps identified. Moreover, this study also looked into the implementation of policies and programs related to adolescent pregnancy. To aid with the analysis, the precede-proceed model and health promotion model were adopted in this study. Likewise, this study identified the existing community health programs and interventions to address teenage pregnancy, existing health policies on teenage pregnancy, and issues and gaps in the implementation. These data were generated from the City Health Office and City Council Office of Tabaco City. The study employed social assessment and ecological assessment. Social assessment determined the social problems and needs identified in Tabaco City, while ecological assessment identified administrative and policy factors that influence implementation policies, programs and nursing interventions. Moving forward, this study also identified the desired outcomes and program implementation. This involved identification of the policies and programs implemented, including availability of resources. This study measured whether or not the policies and programs are implemented, their target population reached, and their desired goals achieved.

Methodology

This study is a qualitative research method. This is a phenomenological research maximized phenomenologic inquiry on what participants experienced and how they interpret these

experiences. Through this, the study has attempted to understand people's perceptions, perspectives and understandings of a particular situation. This study used existing data collected from the Tabaco City Legislation Office or City Council and City Health Office. The information essential to this investigation include teenage pregnancy preventive program; existing health policies on teenage pregnancy; challenges met in the implementation of health programs and policies; and, most importantly, the experience of the teenage pregnancy program implementers.

The experiences in the implementation of the health programs and policies were generated through one-on-one interviews with adolescents, program implementers, and other key informants.

Audio recording was used during the conduct of the interview. Coding was utilized in treating the participants in the study. The information collected was categorized and thematized. Ultimately, the researcher utilized the results to see the gaps and came up with measures to be recommended which can aid in addressing the teenage pregnancy in Tabaco City. Letters of intent to conduct the study were sent to involved institutions prior to the conduct of the study. Likewise, before and after the conduct of the interviews, informed consent was explained and acquired, and that the privacy and confidentiality of the participants were upheld with utmost importance.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Model

Results & Disucssion

The participants in the study were composed of three adolescents who reside in Tabaco City, six public health nurses as program implementers, and two other key informants. All the names of the participants and key informants have been changed to codes or pseudonyms for confidentiality. All the participants can speak and understand Tagalog, Bicol, and English.

The information gathered from the participants of the study suggests the need to strengthen interventions to prevent teenage pregnancy in Tabaco City through the establishment of a sustainable **teenage pregnancy prevention program** supported by an ordinance with budget allocation. Equally important is that it should be managed by a working team composed of skilled health professionals equipped with skills in effective communication, policy advocacy, teaching, counselling, research, and program development. Moreover, program components that include partnership and linkage building, training and education, documentation and research, and communication and media advocacy are deemed highly essential.

Themes	Subthemes
Health education on the ground	Educating the adolescents Creating young leaders and advocates
Engaging society	Involving communities and parents Building linkages and collaboration Engaging the youth
Gaps in skills drawn from experiences	Lacking skills on research Lacking skills on communicating advocacy
Facing human resources problems	Overloaded work and lack of manpower
Institutional challenges	Limited resources Sustaining the program Lacking teenage pregnancy prevention program

It is worth noting that a study showed that teenage pregnancy rates were 39% lower among young individuals receiving an intervention than in those receiving standard practice or no intervention (A Harden 2009). All young people need comprehensive sexuality education to prepare them for healthy adult relationships, and sexuality education programs should broaden adolescents' knowledge and help them to explore attitudes, feelings, and values about human development, relationships, dating, gender roles, sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and healthy sexual decision-making (Advocates for Youth, 2008).

One minor finding is the need to mainstream awareness of people in Tabaco City, especially the adolescents, on the existing adolescent health programs and how they can access services and information. Engaging the youth to participate has been verified in a number of literature and studies that work in addressing issues concerning young people, including teenage pregnancy. Engaging and involving the adolescents as peer educators can be an important educational mechanism for teaching students information and skills to promote sexual health as a teenage pregnancy prevention strategy (Layzer, Rosapep, & Barr, 2017).

The study was not able to identify the health determinants of the adolescent to be able to set priorities and goals. The study was only able to identify the target population which were the adolescents and the environmental determinants which include administrative and policy factors that influence the implementation of interventions, obtained from the narratives of the participants in the study. The limitation of this study was the lack of impact assessment and evaluation of the interventions and programs being implemented in Tabaco City. It exclusively made use of the experiences of the public health nurses. Cross-checking the impact and evaluation of the interventions with the subjective experiences of the public health nurses could have resulted in a wider range of recommendations to address the increasing rate of teenage pregnancies in Tabaco City. To improve adolescent health interventions, potential effective interventions and areas of research for adolescent health and well-being should include interventions for adolescent sexual and reproductive health, nutrition for pregnant adolescents and interventions for substance abuse (Salam, Das, Lassi & Bhutta, 2016). Along program effectiveness and efficiency, to address the gaps in looking at the impact of programs in addressing sexuality-related issues like STIs, HIV, and teenage pregnancy is the conduct of studies in which the researchers must overcome common limitations in study design, analysis, and reporting that have negatively affected prior

researches (Goesling, Colman, Trenholm, Terzian & Moore, 2014). Furthermore, evaluation efforts related to performance improvement and measuring long-term impact are an essential part of attempting to implement an effective teen pregnancy prevention intervention and to determine if the initiative is an adolescent health intervention worth replicating (Tevendale, Condrón, Garraza, House, Romero, Brooks & Walrath, 2017).

Adolescents consider teenage pregnancy prevention as something positive, however, adolescents do not proactively seek assistance in order to obtain information about the topic. Therefore, it is essential to raise awareness and promote professional training in order to implement actions that are in line with public policies, in a creative and innovative way so as to establish a link (Fiedler, Araújo, & de Souza, 2015). The interventions of the teenage pregnancy prevention program in Tabaco City are on health education and advocacy: adolescent sexuality and reproductive health education for the young people, and advocacy measures to encourage parents, communities and other stake-holders or agencies to be actively involved in teenage pregnancy prevention programs. The experiences of public health nurses as adolescent health program implementers to prevent teenage pregnancy showed strength along establishing partnerships and linkages, involving the community, and engaging the youth. However, full implementation is limited due to lack of manpower, resources, and technical skills along data gathering and management, monitoring and evaluation, and demand creation. The development and implementation of legislation, policies and programs to support the needs of public health nurses to promote health and prevent teenage pregnancy are necessary. Research and evidence-based practice has shown that teenage pregnancy cannot be addressed through a single intervention or service inasmuch as teenage pregnancies are unplanned. Instead, a consistent and coordinated partnership approach at a strategic and operational level across schools, health, youth services, social care, and voluntary sector organizations be required to deliver improved outcomes (Teasdale, 2014). Community-wide campaigns to prevent adolescent pregnancy and childbearing are needed because practitioners work with complex social issues such as teenage pregnancy, violence, alcohol, and substance abuse and other health related issues, hence, single solutions are inadequate (Moncloa, Johns, Gong, Russell, Lee & West, 2003).

Tabaco City at present has a strong executive and legislative support to attend to the increasing teenage pregnancy rate and to establish a teenage pregnancy prevention program. To reinforce the initiatives addressing teenage pregnancy in Tabaco City, it is recommended to invest in young people by capacitating the public health nurses with effective communication, policy advocacy, teaching, counselling, research, and program development. Recruiting additional personnel is also recommended. Investing in adolescent health and welfare programs is vital to ensure that services are available through sustainable funding support and legislated policies. Multiple understandings of sustainability and health promotion policy change were identified including the importance of diverse stakeholders working together in coalition and social networks; their distinct positions of power within their political contexts; the role of science versus advocacy in change processes; the particular challenges for public sector health promotion professionals; and other facilitators versus barriers to action (Mendes, Plaza & Wallerstein 2014).

Sustaining and strengthening the partnership and linkages with line agencies, especially with the schools and DepEd are vital in delivering sexuality and reproductive health education to adolescents. Likewise, training and education as a component should be enhanced and existing modules like U4U and materials on adolescent be upscaled. On the other hand, documentation and research and communication and media advocacy be developed.

Conclusion

The findings of the study point towards the strengthening of teenage pregnancy prevention interventions through a creation of **Teenage Pregnancy Prevention Program** supported by a policy with budget allocation for program implementation, including operation, staff, and staff-development.

Legislative and executive support to the issue results in the program and policy to be fully implemented. However, it is important to consider the workforce and their capacities to ensure quality of service in the implementation of teenage pregnancy preventive programs.

Future researchers may look into the impact of the teenage pregnancy prevention interventions being conducted in Tabaco City. Further study can also be done along the health determinants of teenage pregnancy and early sex of young people in Tabaco City.

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